

NURSES' PERCEPTIONS OF THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE ON NURSES' TURNOVER INTENTION IN HOSPITALS

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Abstract

Organizational culture is an integrated pattern resulting from the behavior of individuals in the organization including thoughts, and actions that are learned and taught to the next generation. Turnover intention is the tendency or desire of employees to stop working or move out of the organization where they currently work. Thus, high turnover in hospitals can indicate low employee motivation, morale, and productivity, as well as impact the costs incurred for recruitment, training, and placement of employees. Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research that analyses the influence of organizational culture on nurse turnover in hospitals. The study was conducted using an analytical survey with a cross-sectional study approach. The sampling technique in this study used purposive sampling with a sample size of 84 respondents. The respondents of this study were all nurses of Indriati Solo Baru Hospital. Organizational culture questionnaire and Turnover Intention questionnaire were used to measure the effect of organizational culture on nurses' turnover intention. This research analysis included t-test, F-test and R-square test. The results showed that the characteristics of respondents were mostly women (57.1%) with age 20-30 years (47.6%), the last education was diploma (56%) with tenure ≥ 2 years (40.5%)... Organisational culture has an influence on nurse turnover intention in hospitals.

Keywords: Nurses Perceptions, Organizational Culture, Turnover Intention.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational culture is an integrated pattern resulting from the behavior of individuals in the organization including thoughts, and actions that are learned and taught to the next generation. Organizational culture serves as a glue, unifier, identity, image, and brand, which is different from other organizations (1). One of the problems often faced in organizations is employee turnover, which can be defined as the number of employees who leave divided by the total number of employees who leave and enter in one year, multiplied by one hundred percent. The occurrence of turnover starts from the employee's desire to leave his/her job, which is referred to as turnover intention. High turnover intention reflects a decrease in employee motivation and productivity (2).

High turnover intention reflects a decrease in employee motivation and productivity. The research results of several hospitals in Medan experienced high turnover rates of around 25% to 34%. One hospital in East Java also experienced a high turnover rate of 32% in 2010 although in 2013 it had decreased to 16%. This turnover rate is higher than the ideal turnover rate, which is 5-10% per year (3). The occurrence of turnover begins with turnover intention, which is the desire of employees to leave work. Employee exit interest that arises can also be called turnover intention. Turnover intention by definition is the awareness to think, desire and plan to leave the job (4).

Research on nurse turnover is important because nurses play a key role in the quality of hospital services. Nurse turnover caused by hospital organisational behavioural conditions has been a major focus in hospitals in Australia and the United States. The high turnover rate is caused by an uncondusive work culture, lack of managerial support, workload, and stress, which results in a decrease in the quality of service in the hospital (5).

The researcher conducted a preliminary study by means of unstructured interviews with nursing management at the hospital, which showed that in the last three years there has been a problem of increasing the number of senior nurses who turnover. As a result, the management found it difficult to distribute nurses in the nursing unit and the same thing was also expressed by the human resources department. The results of these interviews were confirmed through interviews with nurses who were still working, with the result that there was a decrease in organizational culture and the workload was getting higher due to the number of nurses leaving. The results of interviews with nurses who have resigned from the hospital are that the work environment in the hospital is not conducive.

METHOD

This type of research is quantitative research with a cross-sectional research design, where data collection is carried out at the same time to determine the effect of organizational culture on nurse turnover in hospitals. The dependent variable in this study is organizational culture, while the independent variable is turnover.

The research was conducted at Indriati Solo Baru Hospital from January to February 2024. The sampling technique in this study used purposive sampling using the Slovin formula. The total sample in this study was 84 respondents. Respondents of this study were all nurses who worked at Indiari Solo Baru hospital and were willing to be respondents. This study used an organizational culture questionnaire and a Turnover Intention questionnaire. The results of validity and reliability tests on this questionnaire have been carried out. The research design used was an analytical survey with a cross-sectional study approach

The analyses used in this study include univariate and bivariate tests. Univariate analysis was used to determine the characteristics of research respondents. Bivariate analyses included t-test, F-test and R-square test(6).

RESULTS

Table 1: Description of Demographic Characteristic

Respondent Characteristics	Frequency (n=84)	Presentation (%)
Gender		
Female	55	65.5
Male	29	34.5
Age (Years)		
20 - 30	39	46.4
31 - 40	32	38.1
> 41	13	15.5
Period of Service		
1 years	24	28.6
>1 years	19	22.6
±2 years	41	48.8
Level of Education		

Diploma	47	56.0
Bachelor	37	44.0
Work Unit		
Hospitalisation	32	38.1
ICU	15	6
IGD	11	13.1
IBS	12	14.3
Polyclinic	12	14.3
Haemodialysis	9	10.7
PONEK	3	3.6

Based on **Table 1**, the distribution of respondent characteristics based on gender was obtained, 65.5% of respondents were female, while 34.5% were male. Based on age, the majority of respondents are in the age range of 20-30 years, which is 46.4%, while the minority is in the age range >41 years, which is 15.5%. 48.8% had worked in the hospital for more than 2 years. In terms of the latest education, the majority of respondents had a D3 education, 56%. In addition, in terms of work units, the majority of respondents were in the inpatient unit as many as 38.1% of respondents.

Table 2: Organisational Culture and Turnover Intention Distribution

Variable	Frequency (n=84)	Presentation (%)
Organisational Culture		
Good	41	48.8
Bad	43	51.2
Turnover Intention		
Low	38	45.2
Medium	24	28.6
High	22	26.2

Based on **Table 2** the results of organizational culture in nurses working at Indriati Solo Baru Hospital, in table 2. it is explained that the majority of respondents have a bad level of organizational culture, namely 51.2%, while the other 48.8% are at a good level of organization. The results of turnover intention is explained that the majority of respondents have a low level of turnover intention, namely 45.2%, while at medium and high turnover intention 28.6% and 26.2%.

Table 3: Result of regression test Turnover Intention

Dependent Variable	Regression Coefficient	T _{obtained}	t _{tabel}	Sig	Test decision
Constant	-0.499	-0.954			
Age	0.066	0.424	1.667	0.673	H0 is accepted
Gender	0.625	3.322	1.667	0.001	H0 is rejected
Period of service	0.170	1.278	1.667	0.205	H0 is accepted
Level of Education	0.410	2.385	1.667	0.020	H0 is rejected
Work Unit	0.064	0.153	1.667	0.172	H0 is accepted
F _{obtained}	= 4.105				
Sig	= 0.002				
Decision	= H0 is rejected				
R	0.456				
Ajd R ²	0.158				

$$Y=b_0+b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3+b_4+b_5X_5 +e$$

Y= Turnover Intention

X₁= Age

X_2 = Gender

X_3 = Period of service

X_4 = Level of Education

X_5 = Work Unit

b_0 = constant

b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5 = Regression coefficient

Regression Equation

In this equation formula only the significant variables are included

Turnover Intention = -0.499+0.066. Age+ 0.625. Gender+ 0.170. Period of service + 0.410. Level Ov Education+ 0.064. Work unit

The regression constant value is 0.336, meaning that if the five independent variables are constant (= 0). Table 1 shows that partially significant test results show that the variables of age, gender, latest education, tenure and work unit are significant to the patient's organizational culture partially does not have a positive and significant on organizational culture.

The t-test shows that age, gender, length of service, latest education, and work unit are determinants of turnover intention (p value = <0.05) and have a positive and significant effect.

Regression analysis shows the coefficient of determination (R-squared) of 0.456. This value indicates that the influence of age, gender, tenure, latest education, and work unit on organizational culture is 45.6%, and the remaining 54.4% is explained by other factors outside this regression model, as moderate variables not examined in this study.

The F test shows a statistically significant influence on the predictors of age, gender, length of service, latest education, and work unit on turnover intention simultaneously F value > F table (p value < 0.05).

Table 4: F-test result Turnover Intention

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	11.865	5	2.373	4.105	0.002
Residual	45.087	78	0.578		
Total	56.952	84			

The F test shows that statistically, there is a significant influence on the predictors of age, gender, latest education, tenure, and work unit on the organizational culture F value > F table (p -value > 0.05) (see Tabel 6).

The analysis results revealed $F_{obtained} > F_{table} = 4.105 > 2.217$ This means that age, gender, latest education, tenure, and work unit variables significantly influenced the dependent variable (p -value < 0.002).

Table 5: Result of regression test Organization Culture

Dependent Variable	Regression Coefficient	T _{obtained}	t _{tabel}	Sig	Test decision
Constant	0.336	2.1350			
Age	0.231	1.5970	1.667	0.114	H0 is accepted
Gender	0.203	1.7660	1.667	0.081	H0 is accepted
Period of service	-0.041	-0.2800	1.667	0.780	H0 is accepted
Level of Education	0.180	1.6380	1.667	0.105	H0 is accepted
Work Unit	0.048	-0.4100	1.667	0.683	H0 is accepted
F _{obtained}	= 1.959				
Sig	= 0.094				
Decision	= H0 is accepted				
R	0.334				
Ajd R ²	0.055				

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4 + b_5X_5 + e$$

Y= Organizational Culture

X₁= Age

X₂ = Gender

X₃ = Period of service

X₄ = Level of Education

X₅ = Work Unit

b₀ = constant

b₁, b₂, b₃, b₄, b₅ = Regression coefficient

Regression Equation

In this equation formula, only the significant variables are included

Organisational Culture = 0.336+0.231.Age+ 0.203. Gender+ (-0.041). Period of service+ 0.180. Level Ov Education+ 0.048. Work unit

The regression constant value is 0.336, meaning that if the five independent variables are constant (= 0). Table 1 shows that partially significant test results show that the variables of age, gender, latest education, tenure and work unit are important to the patient's organizational culture partially does not have a positive and significant on organizational culture.

The t-test shows that age, gender, length of service, latest education and work unit are determinants of organizational culture (pvalue = >0.05) and have a negative and insignificant effect. Regression analysis shows the coefficient of determination (R-squared) of 0.334. This value indicates that the influence of age, gender, tenure, latest education and work unit on organizational culture is 33.4%, and the remaining 66.6% is explained by other factors outside this regression model, as moderate variables not examined in this study.

The F test shows a statistically significant influence on the predictors of age, gender, length of service, latest education and work unit on organizational culture simultaneously F value < F table (p value > 0.05).

Table 6: F-test result Organisational Culture

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	2.342	5	0.468	1.959	0.094
Residual	18.647	78	0.239		
Total	20.988	84			

The F test shows that statistically, there is a significant influence on the predictors of age, gender, latest education, tenure and work unit on the organizational culture F value > F table (p-value > 0.05) (see Tabel 6).

The analysis results revealed $F_{obtained} > F_{table} = 1.959 < 2.217$ This means that age, gender, latest education, tenure and work unit variables not significantly influence the dependent variable (p-value > 0.094).

DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Based on the results of the study, the majority of female respondents were 55 respondents (65.5%). In line with Mulyani et al., (2023) research conducted at the Mitra Sehat Lamongan Surgical Hospital found that the majority of female respondents were 52.8% (7). In addition, Sulastri et al. (2019) found that most of the respondents were female as many as 159 respondents (68.8%) (8). Gender affects a person's decision to choose a job. So far, the majority of nursing is female, this is because women have the advantage of care, namely being more patient and painstaking in dealing with patients (9). According to Kristianti & Sarsono, (2020) in Indonesian society, men and women are perceived to fulfil different roles at work and at home. Therefore, these role differences create differences in their attachments, men are very attached to work while women are very attached to family (10).

Based on the results of this study, it was found that the majority of respondents were aged 20-30 years as many as 39 respondents (47.6%). In line with Maulidah et al., (2022) it was found that most respondents had an age range of 20 to 30 years (11). According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health, age categories can be divided into three, namely early adolescence 17-25 years, early adulthood 26-35 years, late adulthood 36-45 years, and early elderly 46-55 years. Early adulthood (26-35) years is a productive age and can take part in ongoing activities. Age can affect performance until it continues to grow (12).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that most respondents had a work period of ± 2 years as much as 48.8%. In line with the researchers Nursyamsiyah & Qamariyah, (2022) it was found that most of the respondents with a working period of more than 2 years (13). This is because the work experience gained by a person greatly affects his abilities and it is assumed that the longer a person works, the better his abilities will be. Long work will make better experience and have adapted to the organizational culture in their work environment (14).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that most of the respondents had the last Diploma education as much as 56%. In line with Hartati & Pandi, (2020) it was found that most respondents had a diploma education level of 57% (15). This is because the level of education can improve the ability of nurses to provide nursing care both in intellectual, technical, and interpersonal (16). This is in line with Lisnawati

et al., (2022) that a high level of education can strengthen that the higher a person's education, the greater the desire to utilise their knowledge and skills (14).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that most of the respondents in the inpatient work unit were 38.1%. In line with the researcher Hasanah et al., (2020) found that most respondents with inpatient work units were 49.4% (17). As one of the health workers in the hospital, the nursing profession plays an important role in the hospital by providing health services in the form of health in the form of comprehensive bio social, cultural, spiritual nursing care to individuals, families, groups and communities. Maintaining good performance so that it can provide quality services for patients in the form of nursing care (18).

Analysis Of The Influence Of Respondent Characteristics On Hospital Organisational Culture

Based on the results of the study, the p-value of 0.114 means that there is an influence of age on organizational culture. Age can influence organizational culture in several ways. In organizations that are still in the early growth stages, the assumptions and values of the founders can shape the culture, and as the organization develops, the organization can maintain effective practices and abandon ineffective practices. An organization's age and stage of evolution can also affect its culture, with different business and people challenges at each stage (19).

Based on the results of the study, the p-value of 0.081 means that there is no effect of gender on organizational culture. This is because organizational culture is a tool to unite every individual who carries out activities together in an organizational hierarchy that represents the norms of behavior followed by members of the organization. In addition, there is an agreement within the culture that refers to a shared system of meaning, adopted by members of the organization in distinguishing one organization from another. Organizational culture can be determined by the conditions of teamwork, leaders and characteristics of organizations and the prevailing administration process (20).

Based on the results of the study, the p-value of 0.105 means that there is no effect of the last education on organisational culture. In line with Anggreni, (2021) organizational culture affects education. Among them are increasing knowledge, adding insight, exercising leadership skills, learning to divide time, learning to work with teams, improving abilities in the public and so on, organizational culture is very important and also affects education and human resources (21). Because the organization is a work association with the same goal with vision and mission it will be very useful to support the quality of education through led resources. However, it is not just random in choosing an organization, you must first know the vision and culture of the organization, whether it is really good and has a positive impact on those who follow it or vice versa (22).

Based on the results of the study, the p-value of 0.685 means that there is no effect of work units on organizational culture. According to researcher Rannu et al., (2023) organizational culture is more dominantly influenced by the stability indicator, which means that nurses are consistent in maintaining a good culture adopted by members of the organization in the hospital to maintain stability and run according to applicable procedures so that nurses feel a healthy, safe and pleasant atmosphere while working (23). So it can be concluded that stability greatly affects how nurses work and will make nurses feel that the organisational culture created between nurses will have a good impact on the quality of performance produced. So it can be concluded that the better

the Organisational Culture applied by a nurse, the more performance results the nurse will produce (24).

Analysis Of The Effect Of Respondent Characteristics On The Risk Of Hospital Turnover

Based on the results of the study, it is found that there is an effect of gender on the risk of turnover intention with a p-value of 0.018. In line with research conducted by Qowi et al., (2019) obtained a p value of 0.036 which means that there is an influence of gender on turnover intention. The high turnover intention in women is due to their roles and responsibilities as a woman in the family and in her career. These responsibilities include educating children and doing other household chores. In addition, many female nurses move to follow their husbands who work elsewhere (25).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there is no effect of age on the risk of turnover intention with a p-value of 0.081. different from the research conducted by Liu et al., (2023) research conducted in 15 Chinese hospitals with 1815 respondents obtained a p-value of 0.001 which means that there is an effect of age on turnover intention. This is because younger employees are more likely to leave, this may be because easier employees have more opportunities to get a new job and have smaller family responsibilities compared to older employees (26). Meanwhile, employees with old age are reluctant to move four jobs for various reasons such as family responsibilities, decreased mobility, do not want the hassle of moving jobs and starting work in a new workplace, or reduced energy, and more so because of seniority that is not necessarily obtained in the new workplace even though the salary and facilities are greater (27).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there was an influence of the last education on the risk of turnover intention with a p-value of 0.020. In line with researchers Suryani & Heryana, (2019) research conducted at Hermina Hospital and Mogot results that there is an effect of education on turnover intention with a p-value of 0.028. Low levels of education will view difficult tasks as pressure and a source of anxiety. Conversely, if you have a higher level of education, you will feel bored quickly with monotonous work. This is because employees will be more willing to leave and look for new jobs than those with limited education, due to their limited intelligence (27).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there is no effect of period of service on the risk of turnover intention with a p-value of 0.205. In line with Liu et al., (2023) obtained a p-value of 0.027 which means that there is an influence of tenure on turnover intention (26). In addition, younger nurses are usually less experienced and lack effective communication skills that do not meet the requirements of clinical work, leading to increased concerns about errors in their work and greater stress. With longer tenure in the workplace, nurses gain additional experience and opportunities for self-realization and enjoy decision-making power on the job thus, turnover intention decreases (28).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there was no effect of work units on the risk of turnover intention with a p-value of 0.172. In line with the researcher Qowi et al., (2019) obtained the results of p-value > 0.05 which means that there is no effect of work units on the risk of turnover intention (25). This will have an impact on each unit that has a different workload which can cause fatigue, fatigue for nurses and poor communication between nurses and patients. Turnover problem is one of the problems in organizations that is often found regarding human resources (29).

Analysis Of The Effect Of Organisational Culture On Turnover Risk

Based on the results of the study, it is found that there is an effect of organizational culture on turnover intention with a p-value of 0.001. In line with researcher Niguse, (2019) there is a significant relationship between organizational culture and employee turnover intention (30). In line with Kwakye, (2019) research conducted on the administrative staff of private universities in Ghana using 203 respondents found that there is a significant relationship between organizational culture and turnover intention (19).

This is because the stronger the organizational culture, the lower the turnover intention of employees. An organizational culture that is well accepted and followed by all members of the organization is very important in retaining employees. Through a strong organizational culture that creates a comfortable and pleasant work environment, it can make millennial employees feel at home and stay in the organization. An organizational culture that runs fairly on values, norms and all forms of policies on the system (salary, incentives, bonuses, career paths), makes employees not leave the organization. Employees will think twice about leaving their organization for the benefits they receive both physically and psychologically from the comfortable organizational environment of the applied organizational culture (31).

In contrast to research conducted by Kalsum et al., (2023) found that organizational culture does not have a positive and insignificant effect on turnover intention. This means that a higher organizational culture can reduce the level of turnover intention of nurses. A positive organizational culture can support positive behavior and be able to motivate where it tends to encourage nurses to work hard with each other. This can be encouraged by giving nurses the right to work flexibility in completing work, the organization's tolerance for risky work, clarity about suggestions and expectations of the achievements that the organization wants to achieve, superior support including in terms of communication and overall nurse commitment to the organization will form a good organizational culture. If nurses do these things happily and without any coercion from any party, it will reduce turnover intention (32).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there was no effect of characteristics (age, gender, latest education, tenure and work unit) on organizational culture with the results of p-value > 0.05.

Based on the results of the study, there is an influence of characteristics (gender, age, last education, and tenure) on turnover intention with the results of p-value < 0.05. While the work unit has no effect on turnover intention with a p-value of 0.528.

Based on the results of the study, it is found that there is an influence of organizational culture on turnover intention with a p-value of 0.001.

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